

SECTION OF MATHEMATICS, PHYSICS AND INFORMATICS

CONSEQUENCES OF IDEAS ABOUT THE INTERACTION OF PHYSICAL BODIES IN TIME

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Abstract

Analysis interaction of physical bodies in time leads to the following conclusions:

1. The force of inertia is the forces of interaction of the temporal states of the
2. The results of real experiments built on Wheeler's scheme are explained
3. Charges of different signs occur when a body moves at a speed greater than the speed of light (Einstein's formula for mass).
4. The energy of the particle (Einstein's formula $E = mc^2$) consists of the kinetic energy of the protoparticle at $v < c$ and the energy of the moving charge at $v > c$.
5. Way to resolve the paradox of the equality of spin and magnetic moment of an electron and a proton when their masses (and assumed different diameters) are distinguished.

Keywords: Wheeler experiment, inertial force, particle structure, dualism.

Introduction

The exceptional position of the force of inertia was clear to Newton, who even conducted experiments to establish the correspondence of inert and gravitational masses. Existing ideas about the force of inertia caused the need to check the coordinate system for inertia. In the present work, the idea of the interaction of the states of physical bodies in time is developed, which allows us to consider the force of inertia as a kind of interaction inherent in all other known forces.

Analysis of the interaction of temporal states

Newton's third law (equality of the forces of interaction of each of the bodies) is fulfilled by means of a commutative form characteristic of all known laws of interaction. When physical bodies are localized in time, the force of interaction of their temporal states is represented in the form of

$$F_{12} = F_{21} = \frac{I_1 I_2}{jc \Delta t_{12}} \quad (1)$$

- I_1, I_2 - indicators of the temporal states of the body, $jc \Delta t_{12}$ - the time interval between

Introduction
Analysis of the interaction of temporal states (the well-known idea of imaginary time is used).

$$F_Y = -\frac{m}{\Delta t} \sqrt{\frac{v}{1-\left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}} \left(\sqrt{\frac{v+\Delta v}{1-\left(\frac{v+\Delta v}{c}\right)^2}} - \sqrt{\frac{v-\Delta v}{1-\left(\frac{v-\Delta v}{c}\right)^2}} \right) = -\frac{m}{\Delta t} \frac{\sqrt{v}}{\sqrt{1-\left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}} \left(\frac{\sqrt{v}\left(1+\frac{\Delta v}{2v}\right)}{\sqrt{1-\left(\frac{v+\Delta v}{c}\right)^2}} - \frac{\sqrt{v}\left(1-\frac{\Delta v}{2v}\right)}{\sqrt{1-\left(\frac{v-\Delta v}{c}\right)^2}} \right) \quad (4)$$

In the assumption $\Delta v \ll v$, we get the classical expression for the force of inertia.

For uniform circular motion, the force of inertia (centrifugal force) arises as the result of two equal forces of interaction directed at an angle to each other.

$$F_{cf} = -\frac{mv^2}{R \sqrt{1-\left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}} \quad (5)$$

v - velocity of the body, R - is the radius of the circle.

For indicators of the temporal state, it is logical to use a quadratic form, similar to the amplitude of probability in quantum mechanics.

Based on Einstein's formula ($E = mc^2$), let's write down the indicator in the form

$$I = \sqrt{\frac{mc^2 \Delta x}{\sqrt{(\Delta x)^2 + (jc \Delta t)^2}}} = \sqrt{\frac{mcv}{j \sqrt{1-\left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}}} \quad (2)$$

Under the root is that part of the energy of the body that falls on the real part of the Lorentz interval.

Consider the case of the rectilinear uniformly accelerated motion of the self. Given the influence of neighboring temporal states (past and future) in the case of accelerated motion, we obtain a relativistic representation of the force of inertia. A body moving at velocity v (indicator I_0) will interact with adjacent temporary states:

past: velocity $v - \Delta v$ (indicator I_-),

future : velocity $v + \Delta v$ (indicator I_+).

The resulting force has the form:

$$F_Y = \frac{I_0(I_+ - I_-)}{jc \Delta t} \quad (3)$$

As a result

$$F_Y = -\frac{m}{\Delta t} \frac{\sqrt{v}}{\sqrt{1-\left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}} \left(\frac{\sqrt{v}\left(1+\frac{\Delta v}{2v}\right)}{\sqrt{1-\left(\frac{v+\Delta v}{c}\right)^2}} - \frac{\sqrt{v}\left(1-\frac{\Delta v}{2v}\right)}{\sqrt{1-\left(\frac{v-\Delta v}{c}\right)^2}} \right) \quad (4)$$

The minus in the force formula is a sign of the repulsive force (for equally accelerated rectilinear motion, it means the opposite of the force and velocity vectors. Thus, the force of inertia corresponds to the general definition of force [1] and removes the question of the correspondence of inertial and gravitational masses. The results of Wheeler's real experiments become clear with the adopted approach [2-10].

Let's apply the developed approach to the structure of the main charged particles of the proton and electron. The authors do not intend to compete with the well-

known model of the proton, consisting of quarks, moreover, we hope at the next stage to create an adequate model based on them. At the moment, the authors propose a simplified scheme that allows us to explain the paradoxical equality of the angular momentum and magnetic moment of the main elementary particles. It also explains some of the properties of the quarks themselves.

Consider a model of the structure of charged particles (proton and electron). Based on Einstein's formula (the dependence of mass on velocity), suppose the existence of a protoparticle with a mass of m_0 , less than the mass of a proton and rotating in a circle at a speed close to the speed of light. This point of view is due to the localization of the proton, but the choice between the two types of localization (oscillation and rotation) is dictated by the presence of a moment of motion of the particle equal to zero in the case of oscillations.

The centrifugal force acting on the protoparticle with mass is equal to m_0

$$F_{cf} = - \frac{m_0(c-\Delta v)^2}{R \sqrt{\frac{2\Delta v}{c} - \left(\frac{\Delta v}{c}\right)^2}} \quad (6)$$

Δv is a relatively small difference in the velocity of a protoparticle from the speed of light.

Developing the methodology developed in the derivation of the force of inertia, we calculate the indicator of time interaction, which depends on the imaginary fraction of the Lorentz interval

$$I = \frac{mc^2 jc\Delta t}{\sqrt{(\Delta x)^2 + (jc\Delta t)^2}} = \frac{mc^2}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}} \quad (7)$$

Note that in this case, the indicator is focused on describing the interaction of temporary states of charge.

It can be expected that the interaction of temporary states of charge will also differ in sign from the interaction in space, just as the signs of the force of inertia and the force of gravity differ. Let's calculate the value of the interaction force

$$F_{att} = + \frac{m_0cv}{jR \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}} \quad (8)$$

Naturally, suppose that the imaginary unit arises as a result of the motion of the protoparticle at a speed greater than the speed of light by the same amount Δv , (while the average velocity of the two constituent components of the particle is equal to the speed of light) we get

$$F_{att} = + \frac{m_0c(c+\Delta v)}{R \sqrt{\frac{2\Delta v}{c} + \left(\frac{\Delta v}{c}\right)^2}} \quad (9)$$

The assumption leads to the observance of the law ($E = mc^2$) for the sum of the energy of the components of the protoparticle. As a result, we argue that in the case when the protoparticle moves along a circle at a changing speed, there are forces opposite in direction and approximately equal to each other that can localize this particle in space. The model of such a transition deserves special study. Note also that the forces of repulsion and attraction approach each other modulo only in the relativistic interval of velocities.

Therefore, the total energy of the proton can be calculated by the formula

$$E_p = \frac{m_0c^2}{2} \left(\frac{(1-\frac{\Delta v}{c})^2}{\sqrt{\frac{2\Delta v}{c} - \left(\frac{\Delta v}{c}\right)^2}} + \frac{(1+\frac{\Delta v}{c})^2}{\sqrt{\frac{2\Delta v}{c} + \left(\frac{\Delta v}{c}\right)^2}} \right) \quad (10)$$

The key issue is the behavior of a particle (proton) under the influence of an external force. At first glance, this force (within the framework of the above ideas) should act only on the mass component of the proton. However, since centrifugal and centripetal forces must balance each other, it is clear that the action of an external force must affect the change in motion of both the mass and the charge component. As a result, the effective mass of the proton actually doubles and corresponds to the mass in Einstein's formula ($E = mc^2$).

The developed approach outlines a way to explain the paradox of equal spins (and magnetic moments) of a proton and an electron with a catastrophic difference in their masses. With a high degree of probability, the difference in the mass of an electron and a proton is caused by the difference in the sign of their charges. As a result, the sum of the energies of the mass and charge component of the proton should be replaced by the difference in the electron.

Ideas about particle-wave dualism are explained by oscillations of the protoparticle (abrupt change in its velocity). The inequality of the energy of the component (mass - charge) is solved by a model with two equal mass protoparticles with $m_0/2$, the transformation of which occurs in the antiphase. The estimated mass of one protoparticle is close to the upper limit of the total mass of quarks that form a proton. The quark model of the structure of elementary particles (under development) is intended for obtaining known quantitative parameters of particles. Currently, one can only argue that about twice the mass of the D quark (compared to the U quark) is caused by a relatively higher velocity, just as a smaller charge of it also comes from a relatively higher velocity.

Results

A developed idea of the interaction of physical bodies in time provides an explanation of the basic formulas of Einstein's SRT. A path is outlined to explain the equality of spins and magnetic moment of basic elementary particles and their localization in space.

References

1. Parfentev N.A., Patfenteva N.A. Force of Inertia as Sort of Interaction Engineering Mathematics 2021; 5(2): 22-24
2. J. A. Wheeler, pp. 182-213 in Quantum Theory and Measurement, J. A. Wheeler and W. H. Zurek edit., (Princeton University Press, 1984). Figure 4, page 18.
3. Parfentev N. A. Interpretation of the Results of the Real Wheeler's Experience. Engineering Mathematics 2018; 2(2): 86-88.
4. Parfentev N. A. On the nature of the inertia force. Science of Europe. Vol. 1 №30 p. 54-56 2018.
5. P. Grangier, Thèse d'état (1986), Institut d'Optique et Université Paris 11; available online at <http://tel.ccsd.cnrs.fr/tel-0000943>
6. N. Bohr, pp. 9-49 in Quantum Theory and Measurement (Princeton University Press, 1984)
7. G. Greenstein and A. G. Zajonc, The Quantum Challenge (Jones and Bartlett Publishers, 1997)

8. Ma, X. S., Kofler, J. & Zeilinger, A. Delayed-choice gedanken experiments and their realizations. *Rev. Mod. Phys.* 88, 015005 (2016).

9. Manning A. G., Khakimov R. I., Dall R, G., Truscott A. G. Wheeler's delayed-choice gedanken experiment with a single atom. *Nature Physics* volume 11, pages 539–542 (2015).

10. Zhong-Xiao Man, Yun-Jie Xia, Nguyen Ba An Simultaneous observation of particle and wave behaviors of entangled photons *Scientific Reports* volume 7, Article number: 42539 (2017).